

APPROACHES AIMED AT MASTERING THE CONTENT OF THE TEXT THROUGH THE ANALYSIS OF THE "RAVSHAN" EPIC

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Abstract

In this article, in the analysis of the "Ravshan" epic, special attention is paid to approaches aimed at mastering the content of the text, in particular, to the tasks of preparing a presentation using information technologies, interpreting the content of the text. One of the main methodological conditions for working on the text of Ravshan Dostani is to prepare students to understand the text, to read consciously and expressively, to perceive and react. The nature of such preparation is to determine the purpose of the lesson, the content of the material being studied, and to what extent the students have an understanding of it. Students have a strong tendency to complete each task independently. In this period, we are talking about applying approaches that go deeper into the essence of the text, taking into account that the student will be inspired by tasks that he did not encounter in the previous stages.

Key words: Text, artistic text, phrase, graphic painting, fine art, speech development, emotional perception, title, oral statement.

One of the main problems with working on the text is that the lessons are limited to retelling the plot of the work. This is for the students artistic of the work art type as to himself characteristics to their understanding hindrance does

In our opinion, in the process of working on the text, the exact content of the text, its composition, characteristics of the system of images, the writer's ideological intention, the idea of the work, as well as the literary preparation of the class, the age characteristics of the students, the nature of the work, etc. it is appropriate to consider the aspects specific to the analysis of the training. Text in the analysis of the epic "Ravshan" in the 7th grade¹

It is appropriate to prepare a presentation using the following approaches aimed at mastering the content of the text, in particular, using information technologies, and to set the task of interpreting the content of the text:

¹ Yoldoshev Q., Kasimov B., Kadirov V., Yoldoshibekov J. Literature: 7th grade of general secondary education schools, triple-complex. Revised 4th edition /– Tashkent: Sharq, 2017. – pp. 132-167.

Slide 1

“Ravshan” dostoni folklorshunos olim Hodi Zarif tomonidan birinchi marta 1928-yilda Ergash Jumanbulbul o‘g‘li tomonidan yozib olingan. 1941-yilda nashr qilingan.

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“Ravshan” dostoni qofiyali nasrning yorqin namunasi.

Har bir nasriy parcha qofiyalangan bo‘lib, asosan, 7, 8 va 11 bo‘g‘inli barmoq vaznida yaratilgan. 8 bo‘g‘inli vazn urush va jangovarlik holatiga mos.

Keling, kallar, keching jondan,
Umiding bo‘lsa maydondan,
Siz bir yondan, men bir yondan,

Slide 3

Doston qahramonlarining o‘zaro munosabati:

Go‘ro‘g‘li – Avazxon va Havasxon
Avazxon – Gulonor
Qoraxon – Zulxumor
Misqol pari, Yunus pari, Oqqiz
To‘rt pahlavon: Aynoq, Jaynoq, Ersak, Tersak.

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Dostondagi joy nomlari:

Ko‘hi Qof, Eram bog‘i, Vayangan, Xunxor, Yovmit, Shirvon, Chambil.

Slide 5

Dostondagi hayvonlar nomlari:

Jyronqush, G‘irko‘k, Mayna

Slide 6

Dostondagi Zulxumor tasviri:

Jamoli chillaning qoriday tingjirab, yaltirab o‘tirgan. Ana, Zulxumorning ko‘zi jovdirab, zulfi shovdirab, zulfining shu‘lasi yuzga ursa, yarq-yurq etib, betning shu‘lasi zulfiga ursa, yashin tushganday bo‘lib o‘tirdi. Ravshanbek qarasa, musicha, so‘pito‘rg‘ay, g‘azalay, simcha qushlar Zulxumorning jamoli jilvasiga chidamay, baland quyilib kelib, egniga, kaptiga tegib-tegib

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Dostondagi Ravshan tasviri:

Bekning oti po‘lat suvluq chaynaydi,
Qizi kiyib, gulday bo‘lib jaynaydi.
Ilon tili, yashin turli xanjarni
Obro‘ ber deb, xipcha belga boylaydi.
Tomosha qing xon
Ravshanday polvono,
Shirvonning yurtiga talab ayladi.

Slide 8

Dostonda qo‘llanilgan saj’ san’ati namunalari:

Zulxumorning kamoli, oyday jamoli, oq yuzida xoli, yangi to‘lgan
oyday ikki qoshi hiloli. Yasangan hurday, tishlari durday, ko‘zlari
yulduzday, qoshlari qunduzday, lablari qirmizday, og‘izlari
o‘ymoqday, lablari qaymoqday, ikki yuzi oyday, tarlon qarchig‘ay

Art in grades 5-7 work in the analysis to questions wide place _ given _ The teacher's main that's the task questions on work methods in advance set is to get Creative to approach requirement etuv s hi questions the students to creativity directs his thoughts analysis by doing to generalize teaches . Questions and assignments above affairs group , binary and individually _ organize will be done .

the students question to compose to teach Text on at work the students question to compose to teach intended the effect will give . Methodist of scientists to his opinion that 's right _ given in the question half answer ready will be Students _ the text conscious master as long as he can , that's it able to come out they get Make a question teach _ initial from classes start to the goal according to Read the students conscious respectively question to compose to teach for teacher to the text himself made up or in the "Literature" textbook given questions analysis does _ For the analysis " *Why he or this question placed ?*", " *Then who or what* ", " *More questions which words with starts ?*" such as questions uses and text based on answer to give teaches .

Secondly , he is a teacher students attention to the text question make up to the way points and question from making first the text attention with study , participant heroes show question to be built part separate designation necessity on the surface concept will give . Read the students question to compose to teach initial stage this exercise the team being is done because such affairs educational in character will be To this end more convenient question separated , his what for interesting the fact that or the opposite is explained . For example , Anvar Obidjon in the 5th grade " *Life each the moment beautiful hall* " poem² on " *Early in the morning of life Beginning on the surface question compose* " assignment after placing , students

² Ahmedov S. et al. Literature. 5th grade of general secondary schools i textbook for - T.: Sharq, 2020. - p. 235 .

by "How is every morning?" Beginning in the poem how reflection done?" in the content question structure to the goal according to

In the 6th grade, O' is sharp Hashimov's "War". last "victim" story³ on the surface students to the front as follows question make up task to put can :

1) in the work the first paragraph read it and that's it part on the surface question prepare.

2) of the story second in the paragraph given of words the meaning explain according to questions compose ;

3) of heroes behavior , character features or mutually _ relationship on the surface questions make up and etc

In this way students _ creative or discussion in the content questions to give learning the ways they get. In students independent thinking formation to the issue directed scientific in his research Methodist scientist Q. Husanboyeva this to the matter separately attention looks . In particular , "Child's thinking independence his knowledge to get interest , study. of science to the point to enter desire , something event according to harvest done superficial from knowledge not satisfied gave also shown in the questions will be The student's something study science on the surface thoughts , questions how much a lot if so , here it is to the subject has been interest that's all tall that it is to believe can. So , questions not only of interest depth measure , perhaps independent of thinking development sign is also Pedagogical in practice the students question to give exclamation point series methods there is . But the students deep questions to give education in experience so much wide not spread

Teachers each different methods with students question to give , the problem to find and solve does not encourage . He is a teacher by ready and right conclusions to be given in the child mental to strain the need does not wake up the student the subject to learn deep interest surface doesn't come Interest was not in the place there are no questions . "⁴

Indeed , questions new knowledge to get which directs way make up in students being studied object , event , character character feature determine what _ for that it is so to know possibility creates _

Text describe _ Text describe text on at work separately place _ occupied by the students creative abilities develop from it fruitful and reasonable use skills develops . Through this in the work the writer by described vital landscapes sure imagination to do comfortable conditions is created . In methodology text two different road _ with : word with and graph way again description is emphasized .

The word with describe to himself special activity type being , then in the work reflection reached the reality of the hero internal and external appearance , as well as the landscape word through again recovery requirement will be done . Text of the image full-fledged to be of students the text in it the situation , the participants character features in his imagination to embody closely depend _ Word with describe stages planning Professor K. Kasimova special of preparation important aspects as the following shows :

1. From the text landscape , situation or of heroes external appearance _ described seats is determined .

³ S. Ahmedov, R. Kochkarov, Sh. Rizayev 6th grade. Literature: Textbook-complex for the 6th grade of general secondary schools. Revised 4th Edition / . . - Tashkent: Spirituality, 2017. - 148 p.

⁴ Husanboeva Q. Literature is a factor of spirituality and independent opinion formation. - Tashkent: Publishing House of the National Library of Uzbekistan named after Alisher Navoi, 2009. - p. 120.

2. Relative completed places _ is separated .

3. Lexical-methodical preparation for description is carried out, that is, students' attention is drawn to the lexical units used by the writer and poet and they are analyzed. It helps to choose the right word in the description.

4. It is necessary to write down the words to be used in the calligraphy at the beginning of teaching to describe with words ⁵.

It seems that describing the text with words requires the ability to increase the student's vocabulary, to choose the word and use it in its place .

Graphics are mostly done at home. In this case, the students will have to select the part of the text to describe, read it over and over again, and draw a picture according to it. They think about the content of the text by looking at the drawn pictures. As a result, their vocabulary increases, oral speech, logical and creative thinking skills are formed. Teaching students to choose the necessary words in the text consciously and with understanding without excessive difficulty is a necessary aspect of work on the text.

Creating a work plan. The plan helps to consciously and deeply understand the content of the text, to distinguish the main idea, to determine the coherence of the subject, and to understand the connections between the parts of the text. Working on a plan teaches students to divide the content of the text into complete parts, find the basis of each part, give each a clear and concise title, and formulate it as a plan.

In the next step, students will be taught how to move from pictorial planning to logical planning. Makes sense plan make up the following in order take goes to :

1. A teacher by parts separated to the text choose plan is made . Then look text of the plan places replaced by the title to the left of the board writing is placed . Students _ reads part 1 of the text , that's it part to the content suitable title finds.

He is a teacher while of the board right to the side the title writes. In this way on the board died of the text plan is formed .

2. To the text about parts analysis to do to do in the process students _ teacher led by each one in part main the idea determine and to him title they find He is a teacher titles plan based on to the board writing goes.

3. To parts separated text selected titles text plan in order to the board is written . To the students given from the headlines using the text parts separate task is submitted . Text o' to the headlines belongs to part they separate

4. To parts not separated text selected titles mixed without to the board is written . As above parts to be task is submitted . Students the text read , relative completed part determine . To him suitable title from the board they choose That's the thing way continue , text plan is made .

Summary 5th - 7th grade students age , psychological features , type of work and genre features , topic scope artistic work on at work attention taken important has been pedagogical and psychological factors being a student to the person strong effect shows . Theirs knowledge level increase of knowledge to be assimilated provider method and methods efficient apply requires a mechanism .

⁵ Kasimova K. Methodology of mother tongue teaching. - Tashkent: Publisher, 2009. - p. 99.

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